

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15443002

Determination Of Some Heavy Metals In Water From Wells And Boreholes Using Atomic Absorption Spectrometry (AAS) Technique Around Mando, Kaduna State

¹Hussaini S., ¹Onuk O. G., ¹Lawan M. A., ¹Musa B. ³U. Rilwan

¹Department of Physics, Federal University Gashua Yobe State, Nigeria

²Department of Physics, Yobe State University, Damaturu Yobe State, Nigeria

³Department of Physics Army University Biu, Borno State, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

Heavy metals are major source for water contamination, their determination is critical for accessing the safety and quality of water intake and environmental health. Public and environmental health issues are critically depend on the quality of water intake, especially, water sources from wells and boreholes. This research work is aimed at determining heavy metals in water from wells and boreholes using Atomic Absorption Spectrometry (AAS) technique at Mando residential area Kaduna state. Samples were randomly collected from ten different locations across the study area for both well and borehole water and analyzed using atomic absorption spectrometry to determine the concentration of heavy metals. The analysis determined Lead (0.0001-0.0021), Copper (0.2344-0.6727), Zinc (0.0594-2.3516), Magnesium (0.2712-6.1246), Cobalt (0.1460-0.9186), Nickel (0.6725-0.9826) and Mercury (0.0008-0.2002) in varied concentration. The results obtained were compared with guidelines for drinking water quality such as; Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality (NSDWQ). The study showed that; magnesium, Cobalt and Nickel has a higher concentration than that of the acceptable guidelines for drinking water quality therefore, the people living in this area are liable to have the following health challenges; Cancer, mental development in infants, hearing and visual impairment, cardiovascular, endocrine deficits and carcinogenic.

Keywords: water contamination, environmental health, boreholes

INTRODUCTION

One of the fundamental human right that is an essential component for sustainable development is access to clean water. However, the sources of this essential component often get contaminated by heavy metals and other elements. This poses great risk for public health and the environment. Heavy metals can either be toxic or essential to human health even though when in excess often result to toxicity. Metals like that lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), and chromium (Cr) poses serious health risks even at trace level or low concentration, unlike copper (Cu) and zinc (Zn) that are essential for biological functions but toxic at elevated level.

Water with the chemical formula (H_2O) is an inorganic, transparent, tasteless, odourless, and nearly colourless chemical substance, which is the main constituent of Earth's hydrosphere and the fluids of all known living organisms (in which it acts as a solvent). It is vital for all known forms of life, even though it provides no calories or organic nutrients. Its chemical formula indicates that each of its molecules contains one oxygen and two hydrogen atoms, connected by covalent bond. Water is a substance existing in gaseous, liquid, and solid states. It is one of the most plentiful and essential of compounds.

Water is an important component of the earth covering about three quarter (3/4) of the earth's surface and occurs on land, underground and in space, without water life on earth would be impossible, it is often referred to as the "Liquid of life" because it constitutes up to ninety percent (90%) of the cell and serves as medium for the dissolution and transportation of body nutrients and other essential molecules. Without its availability for human use (through drinking) within a maximum of fourteen days, the body becomes dehydrated and life is endangered. In addition, about two thirds of our body is made up of water, about 45 litres in the average adult. The brain is 5 percent water, the muscles 77 percent and the bones 33 percent (Akpan, 1998). According to him we need to drink about two litres a day to stay healthy.

Fresh water that is available for human consumption comes from wells, boreholes, lakes and subsurface aquifers. These sources account for only one (1%) of the entire water on the earth. Today 31 countries representing 2.8 billion people including Nigeria, Kenya, and China, India, and Ethiopia are confronted with chronic problems related to water quality. Within a generation the world's population will climb to an estimated 8 billion people, yet the amount of water will remain the same (Bishno et al, 2007). Contaminants such as Heavy metals, nitrates and salt have found their way into various water supplies due to inadequate treatment and disposal of waste from human and livestock and overuse of limited water resources (Singh et al., 2003) Even if no source of anthropogenic contamination exist, natural sources are also equally potential to contribute higher of some metals and other chemicals that can harm human health (Anawara et al, 2002) Uptake of heavy metals by plant through water and subsequent accumulation along food chain is a potential threat to animal and human health (Borini et al, 2007).

Generally, the quality of drinking water is determined based on the appearance, taste, color and odor of the water. The appearance, taste, color and odor do not really tell if the water is safe to drink. Safe drinking water should also be free from hazardous compounds (Berman, 1980). Water is vital for the existence of life and its importance in our daily life makes it imperative that thorough microbial, physiochemical and heavy metal examination of water should be concluded on water used for various purposes to reduce the risk of water borne diseases emanation from such water. Portable water is the water that is free from disease producing microorganism chemical substances that are dangerous to health (Iaminkera, 1999). In Nigeria, majority of the in the rural and urban area do not have access to portable water and therefore depend on well, stream and river water for domestic use. The bacterial and heavy metal content of well and boreholes water in Nigeria have been reported to be unsatisfactory, with coliform count exceeding the recommendation by World Health Organization.

The World Health Organization assessed that up to 80% of all illnesses on the planet are brought about by a lack of sterilization, contaminated water, or inaccessibility of water.

The overall objective of the flow work is to assess the idea of drinking water around Mando Kaduna state with the following objectives;

- ✓ To ascertain the elevation (longitude and latitude) of the selected well water and boreholes
- ✓ To undertake laboratory examination of the given samples using atomic absorption spectroscopy.
- ✓ To compare the result and the acceptable Nigerian standard for drinking water quality.
- ✓ To educate people on the health impacts of heavy metals present in water.

Heavy Metals Pollution In Water

Pollution of heavy metals poses various societal problems. Heavy metals are known to contaminate neurodevelopment as they can cause reproductive damage that contributes to brain disorders, delays in development, disabilities in the education of children, and misbehaviors. Heavy metal pollution is becoming an environmental problem at the global level due to its adverse effects. These inorganic and toxic heavy metals are discarded into the water ecosystem, soil, sediments, and the atmosphere due to

human activities and rapidly growing urbanization. As a result, these heavy metals enter the environment surrounded by humans, plants, animals and microorganisms, and other living organisms. Once they enter into the environment, they contaminate and cycle in all the spheres of the environment, including the biosphere, lithosphere, hydrosphere, and atmosphere, which are interconnected, Heavy metals become hazardous for human beings when they cannot be metabolized and accumulate into the soft tissue of the body. Although heavy metals are persistent, toxic, and inorganic, they can easily bind covalently with organic groups. Heavy metals form lipophilic ions and compounds with non-metallic elements like proteins generating toxic effects. These metals can easily enter the human body via different pathways, including ingestion of contaminated water and drinking contaminated water from the environment. Heavy metals cannot be broken down and are non-biodegradable, so when they enter the human body, they pose serious hazardous impacts.

Heavy metals are major contributors of neurobehavioral damage, which ultimately affects the IQ level of children and affects their academic attainment. Exposure to heavy metals during the perinatal and early childhood periods increases the risk of autism. Due to their ubiquitous presence, heavy metals and other persistent organic chemicals could significantly affect the neurobiological processes and cause depressive symptoms.

Heavy metals are dangerous because they tend to bio accumulate. Bioaccumulation means an increase in the concentration of a chemical in a biological organism over time, compared to the chemical's concentration in the environment. Compounds accumulate in living things any time they are taken up and stored faster than they are broken down (metabolized) or excreted. Heavy metals can enter a water supply by industrial and consumer waste, or even from acidic rain breaking down soils and releasing heavy metals into streams, lakes, rivers, and groundwater. Heavy metal toxicity can result in damaged or reduced mental and central nervous function, lower energy levels, and damage to blood composition, lungs, kidneys, liver, and other vital organs. Long-term exposure may result in slowly progressing physical, muscular, and neurological degenerative processes that mimic Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, muscular dystrophy, and multiple sclerosis. Allergies are not uncommon and repeated long-term contact with some metals or their compounds may even cause cancer.

The presence of some toxic metals in water is a serious challenge to our society. For this reason, there is a need for careful assessment, monitoring, and control of their use in the environment. Through various socio-economic and industrial activities, man causes severe pollution in the water bodies that leads to serious environmental problems which result in diseases, sudden deaths, and disabilities.

Heavy metals have been investigated on a large scale in different river (Wakida., et al., 2008, Feng et al., 2008, Carolina et al., 2008). The toxicity of heavy metals has long been concerned since it is very important to the health of people and ecology. Heavy metals can also accumulate in the soil at toxic levels as a result of long-term application of untreated waste waters. Soils irrigated by wastewater accumulate heavy metals such as Cr, Zn, Pb, Cd, Ni, etc in surface soil (Sanayei et al., 2009). When the capacity of the soil to retain heavy metals is reduced due to repeated application of wastewater, heavy metals leach into the ground water or soil solution available for plant uptake (Charya et al., 2008).

In Nigeria, the major sources of heavy metals pollution are industrial effluents discharged from various processing industries. This increases the influx of metals, which can be transported by wind and water and thus become available to plants and animals. These heavy metals attain higher concentrations and accumulate in dangerous quantity in different plants' part, and finally pose serious health hazard to human beings and the animals through biomagnification (Ray, 1990). Heavy metals are elements having atomic weight between 63.545 and 200.5g (Kennish, 1992) and a specific gravity greater than four (Connel et al., 1984). The toxicity of these metals has also been demonstrated throughout history: Greek and Roman physicians diagnosed symptoms of acute lead poisoning long before toxicology became a science. Exposure to heavy metals has been linked with developmental retardation, various cancers, kidney damage and even death (Abdulaziz and Mohammed, 1997).

The historical use of land, for example, application of natural manure and artificial fertilizers, over time contaminates the top soil as the trace metals accumulate in the soils and eventually percolate to shallow water tables.

Heavy metals occur naturally in the soil surrounding during pedogenesis at trace levels (<1000 mg/kg) and are rarely poisonous (Pendias and Pendias, 2001). Heavy metals are scarce and their levels in natural, non-reduced under-groundwater are mostly less than Ippm hence, categorized as trace elements. Iron and manganese are most abundant and higher in concentrations. In comparison, the other elements are naturally low in concentration usually below 50 ppm.

Assessment of any of these elements to determine whether the levels are higher or any probable anthropogenic influences, analytical methods using low detection limits are employed (Fresenius, 1994).

Heavy metals are injurious due to their bio-accumulation nature, these metals infiltrate into the water sources through the discharge of industrial and domestic effluent, or even as a result of emitted heavy metals due to acidic rain breaking down soils.

Their bioavailability is dependent on physical parameters for instance; pH, oxygen content, temperature, phase association, adsorption and sequestration (Hamelink, 1994). As concluded by Wang (2001), metal ions interrelate with cell constituents for instance DNA and nuclear proteins resulting into DNA changes and conformational transformations that could lead to cell modification, cancer or cell death.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

Mando is located within latitudes 10°35'26" N and 10°35'24" N and longitudes 7°24'21" E and 7° 24' 18" E, with an elevation of 435 metres (1427.1654 feet) to correct 4dp, it is situated in Igabi Local Government Area of Kaduna, Kaduna State, the area is characterized by agricultural activities and small scale industrial operations. Residents of the study area depends on ground water sources such as well and borehole water for their day to day activities, this makes the study area an ideal location for this research. The area falls within the southeastern part of Kaduna, Kaduna State, Nigeria. Mando is one of the fast developing residential area in Kaduna which has about 7500 residents and inhabited by a mix of different ethnic groups.

Figure; showing Map of Study Area with the Locations from Which Samples were been collected.

Table

S/N	SAMPLE	NAMES OF SAMPLES	SOURCE	LATITUDE	LONGITUDE	ELEVATION
1	A	Hajj Camp	BOREHOLE	10°35'25"N	7°24'18"E	1 . 1 3 k m
2	B	Zangon Daura	W E L L	10°35'26"N	7°24'19"E	1 . 1 3 k m
3	C	Kasuwar Fulani	BOREHOLE	10°35'26"N	7°24'19"E	1 . 1 3 k m
4	D	Mshelia	BOREHOLE	10°35'25"N	7°24'19"E	1 . 1 3 k m
5	E	Sammani	W E L L	10°35'23"N	7°24'19"E	1 . 1 3 k m
6	F	Baffa Ali	W E L L	10°35'25"N	7°24'20"E	1 . 1 3 k m
7	G	Malkali	W E L L	10°35'26"N	7°24'19"E	1 . 1 3 k m
8	H	Yan Kwalta	W E L L	10°35'26"N	7°24'20"E	1 . 1 3 k m
9	I	Mai Jama'a	W E L L	10°35'26"N	7°24'18"E	1 . 1 3 k m
1 0	J	Rumbun Doka	BOREHOLE	10°35'24"N	7°24'21"E	1 . 1 4 k m

METHOD:

Sample collection: A total of 10 samples were collected cross the study area, with five samples from well water sources and five from borehole water sources. The sampling points were selected to represent different locations within the area. Clean, acid-washed polyethylene bottles were used for sample collection to avoid contamination. The samples were labeled, stored in an icebox, and transported to the laboratory for analysis.

Sample Preparation: The water samples were filtered using Whatman filter paper to remove suspended particles. Each sample was acidified with nitric acid to a pH below 2 to preserve the metal ions and prevent microbial growth. The samples were stored at 4°C until analysis.

Instrumentation and Analysis: A PerkinElmer AAnalyst Atomic Absorption Spectrometer equipped with hollow cathode lamps for Pb, Cd, Cr, Cu, and Zn was used for the analysis. The instrument was calibrated using standard solutions prepared from certified reference materials. The detection limits for each metal were determined, and quality control measures, including the analysis of blanks and spiked samples, were implemented to ensure accuracy and precision.

Data Analysis: The concentrations of heavy metals in the water samples were expressed in mg/L. Statistical analysis, including descriptive statistics and correlation analysis, was performed using statistical software to interpret the results and identify patterns in metal contamination.

RESULT ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Clean and pure drinking water is a necessity. That's why governments, contract labs, utilities and regulatory agencies test a high volume of samples, time-sensitive assays, and take on emergency sampling while adhering to strict and often-changing regulations.

Drinking water analysis starts with confidence and our established workflow solutions ensure you get accurate, timely results, day after day. And with faster turnarounds and lab technician turnover adding to your challenges, these simple, effective solutions instill a high level of confidence in your lab and help ensure your communities' water supplies are safe and unadulterated.

Acceptable parameters concentrations (mg/l) from Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality (NSDWQ).

Table : Daily allowed intake of some heavy metals concentration (mg/l) and their Health impact.

PARAMETERS	UNIT	NSDWQ	HEALTH IMPACT
LEAD (Pb)	mg/l	0.0100	Cancer, interference with Vitamin D metabolism, affects mental development in infants, toxic to the central and peripheral nervous systems.
COPPER (Cu)	mg/l	1.0000	Gastrointestinal disorder.
ZINC (Zn)	mg/l	3.0000	No health-based guideline value has been proposed for zinc in drinking-water
NICKEL (Ni)	mg/l	0.0200	Possible carcinogenic.
COBALT (Co)	mg/l	0.005 (WHO)	Neurological (e.g. hearing and visual impairment), cardiovascular and endocrine deficits.
MAGNESIUM (Mg)	mg/l	0.2000	Consumer acceptability.
MERCURY (Hg)	mg/l	0.0010	Affects the kidney and central nervous system.

Note that Cobalt does not have Nigeria Standard. The source of reference is gotten from the World Health Organization (WHO).

Table Concentration of heavy metals in Borehole sample in Hajj Camp

Elements	Zinc	Copper	Lead	Cobalt	Nickel	Magnesium	Mercury
Values	0.5842	0.2459	0.0009	0.1460	0.8264	1.6527	0.0009
NSDWQ	3.0000	1.0000	0.0100	0.005	0.0200	0.2000	0.0010

Figure : Graphical representation of Concentration of heavy metals in Hajj Camp

Figure 4.1 in comparison with Table 4.0 above, it is obvious that Zinc, Copper, Lead, Cobalt and Mercury fell within their Standards. But Nickel with 0.8264mg/l and Magnesium with 1.6527mg/l was found to be higher than their standard. Their health impacts are possible carcinogenic and consumer acceptability

Table ; Concentration of heavy metals in well sample in Zangon Daura

Elements	Zinc	Copper	Lead	Cobalt	Nickel	Magnesium	Mercury
Values	0.5194	0.2534	0.0018	0.3889	0.8723	3.9596	0.0020
NSDWQ	3.0000	1.0000	0.0100	0.005	0.0200	0.2000	0.0010

Figure: Graphical representation of Concentration of heavy metals in Zangon Daura

Figure 4.2 in comparison with Table 4.0 above, it is obvious that Zinc, Copper and Lead and Cobalt fell within their Standards. But Nickel with 0.8723mg/l, Magnesium with 3.9596mg/l and Mercury with 0.0020 was found to be higher than their standard. Their health impacts are possible carcinogenic, consumer acceptability, affects the kidney and central nervous system.

Table: Concentration of heavy metals in Borehole sample in Kasuwar Fulani

Elements	Zinc	Copper	Lead	Cobalt	Nickel	Magnesium	Mercury
Values	0.2530	0.2827	0.0001	0.2306	0.8010	0.9824	0.0014
NSDWQ	3.0000	1.0000	0.0100	0.005	0.0200	0.2000	0.0010

Figure: Graphical representation of Concentration of heavy metals in Kasuwar Fulani

Figure 4.1 in comparison with table 4.0 above, it is obvious that Zinc, Copper, Lead, Cobalt and Mercury fell within their Standards. But Nickel with 0.8010mg/l and Magnesium with 0.9824mg/l was found to be higher than their standard. Their health impacts are possible carcinogenic and consumer acceptability.

Table: Concentration of heavy metals in Borehole sample in Mshelia

Elements	Zinc	Copper	Lead	Cobalt	Nickel	Magnesium	Mercury
Values	2.1943	0.4613	0.0003	0.3367	0.8291	0.3886	0.0008
NSDWQ	3.0000	1.0000	0.0100	0.005	0.0200	0.2000	0.0010

Figure: Graphical representation of Concentration of heavy metals in Mshelia

Figure 4.4 in comparison with table 4.0 above, it is obvious that Zinc, Copper, Lead, Cobalt and Mercury fell within their Standards. But Nickel with 0.8291mg/l and Magnesium with 0.3886mg/l was found to be

higher than their standard. Their health impacts are possible carcinogenic and consumer acceptability.

Table: Concentration of heavy metals in well sample in Sammani

Elements	Zinc	Copper	Lead	Cobalt	Nickel	Magnesium	Mercury
Values	0.3310	0.2412	0.0021	0.3857	0.9826	3.1839	0.2002
NSDWQ	3.0000	1.0000	0.0100	0.005	0.0200	0.2000	0.0010

Figure: Graphical representation of Concentration of heavy metals in Sammani Figure 4.5 in comparison with Table 4.0 above, it is obvious that Zinc, Copper, Lead and Cobalt fell within their Standards. But Nickel with 0.9826mg/l, Magnesium with 3.1839mg/l and Mercury with 0.2020 was found to be higher than their standard. Their health impacts are possible carcinogenic, consumer acceptability, affects kidney and central nervous system.

Table: Concentration of heavy metals in Well sample in Baffa Ali

Elements	Zinc	Copper	Lead	Cobalt	Nickel	Magnesium	Mercury
Values	0.0594	0.2390	0.0010	0.2461	0.9068	1.0729	0.0018
NSDWQ	3.0000	1.0000	0.0100	0.005	0.0200	0.2000	0.0010

Figure: Graphical representation of Concentration of heavy metals in Baffa Ali

Figure 4.6 in comparison with Table 4.0 above, it is obvious that Zinc, Copper, Lead and Cobalt fell within their Standards. But Nickel with 0.9068mg/l, Magnesium with 1.0729mg/l and Mercury with an approximate value of 0.0020mg/l was found to be higher than their standard. Their health impacts are possible carcinogenic, consumer acceptability, affects kidney and central nervous system.

Table: Concentration of heavy metals in Well sample in Malkali

Elements	Zinc	Copper	Lead	Cobalt	Nickel	Magnesium	Mercury
Values	1.0572	0.2378	0.0017	0.6172	0.8079	2.8116	0.0014
NSDWQ	3.0000	1.0000	0.0100	0.005	0.0200	0.2000	0.0010

Figure: Graphical representation of Concentration of heavy metals in Malkali

Figure 4.7 in comparison with table 4.0 above, it is obvious that Zinc, Copper, Lead, Cobalt and Mercury fell within their Standards. But Nickel with 0.8079mg/l and Magnesium with 2.8116mg/l was found to be higher than their standard. Their health impacts are possible carcinogenic and consumer acceptability.

Table: Concentration of heavy metals in Well sample in Yan Kwaha

Elements	Zinc	Copper	Lead	Cobalt	Nickel	Magnesium	Mercury
Values	2.3516	0.2369	0.0011	0.2961	0.6725	1.3972	0.0025
NSDWQ	3.0000	1.0000	0.0100	0.005	0.0200	0.2000	0.0010

Figure: Graphical representation of Concentration of heavy metals in Yan Kwaha

Figure 4.8 in comparison with Table 4.0 above, it is obvious that Zinc, Copper, Lead and Cobalt fell within their Standards. But Nickel with 0.6725mg/l, Magnesium with 1.3972mg/l and Mercury with 0.0025mg/l was found to be higher than their standard. Their health impacts are mentioned in Table 4.0 above. Their health impacts are possible carcinogenic, consumer acceptability, affects kidney and central nervous system.

Table: Concentration of heavy metals in Well sample in Mai Jama'a

Elements	Zinc	Copper	Lead	Cobalt	Nickel	Magnesium	Mercury
Values	1.0773	0.2344	0.0018	0.5045	0.7984	6.1246	0.0015
NSDWQ	3.0000	1.0000	0.0100	0.005	0.0200	0.2000	0.0010

Figure: Graphical representation of Concentration of heavy metals in Mai Jama'a

Figure 4.9 in comparison with table 4.0 above, it is obvious that Zinc, Copper, Lead, Cobalt and Mercury fell within their Standards. But Nickel with 0.7984mg/l and Magnesium with 6.1246mg/l was found to be higher than their standard. Their health impacts are possible carcinogenic and consumer acceptability.

Table: Concentration of heavy metals in Borehole sample in Rumbun Doka

Elements	Zinc	Copper	Lead	Cobalt	Nickel	Magnesium	Mercury
Values	0.0650	0.6727	0.0004	0.9186	0.7456	0.2712	0.0008
NSDWQ	3.0000	1.0000	0.0100	0.005	0.0200	0.2000	0.0010

Figure: Graphical representation of Concentration of heavy metals in Rumbun Doka

Figure 4.10 in comparison with table 4.0 above, it is obvious that Zinc, Copper, Lead, Cobalt and Mercury fell within their Standards. But Nickel with 0.7456mg/l and Magnesium with 0.2712mg/l was found to be higher than their standard. Their health impacts are possible carcinogenic and consumer acceptability.

CONCLUSION

This study was carried out to investigate the concentration of heavy metals ions in well water and boreholes in ten (10) different sample points of Mando. Seven metals were detected in all ten samples.

Wells and boreholes has turned to be the most dominant methods for water supply to the average individual living in the examined region because of lack of capital to have access to clear versatile drinking water. Most potion of well and boreholes are sited close to an artificial waterway (canals), large portion of them are not appropriately shut. Hence the water quality is extremely low.

The study shows that, Nickel, Magnesium and mercury (in some parts) has high concentrations above the NSDWQ maximum permissible limit for Nickel, Magnesium and Mercury at all examined samples point. The concentration of Copper, Lead, Cobalt and Zinc was lower at all sites compared to the NSDWQ standard permissible limit.

Continuous supervision of water quality in Mando region is very important to keep the heavy metal pollution in check, and groundwater consumption as drinking water should be reduced due to potential chemical toxicity risk to humans.

Government should set up certain checking procedure and enable NSDWQ agency for proper guidance and safety in different territories, particularly in the remote places of the investigated areas. Hence continual assessment and enlightenment should be administered to the inhabitants of the investigated areas.

REFERENCES

- Abdulaziz, B.A. and Muhammad, H. (1997): Role of Epidemiological Studies in Determining Environmental Impact on Health in Saudi Arabia. Book of Abstract for the Development and Environmental Impact Conference, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. P. 196
- Akpan G.E. (1998). The Effect of Student Income Support on Academic Performance. The Nigerian Journal of Economic and Social Studies. 40(2).285,293.

- Anawara HM, Akaib J, Mostfac KM, et al. Arsenic poisoning in groundwater health risk and geochemical sources in Bangladesh. *Environ Int.* 2002;27(7):597-604.
- Berman, E. (1980). Toxic metal and their analysis. New York: Hayden and Sons Ltd. Sunway Academic journal 6 Pp 34.
- Connel, B.S., Cox, M. and Singer, I. (1984): Nickel and Chromium In: Brunner, F. and Coburn, J.W. (eds): Disorders of minerals metabolism. Academic press, New York. Pp. 472 – 532.
- Charya, S. N., Kamalaa, C. T and Samuel, S. R (2008): Assessing risk of heavy metals from consuming food grown on sewage irrigated soils and food chain transfer Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety. *Bulletin of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology*, 69:513-524
- Fresenius J. (1994): Determination of heavy metals in groundwater samples- ICP-MS analysis and evaluation, *Anal Chem* 350:204-209.
- Hamelink JL, Landrum PF, Harold BL, William BH, (1994): Bioavailability: Physical, Chemical and Biological interactions. Boca Raton, FL: CRC Press Inc health advisories. *Reviews of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology*, 10 7:25-37.
- Kennish, L. (1992): Toxicity of heavy metals: effects of Cr and Se on humans health. *Journal of Indian Public Health Education, India.* 2:36 – 64.
- Pendias K. and Pendias H. (2001): Trace Metals in Soils and Plants, CRC Press, BocaRaton, Fla, USA, 2nd edition.
- Sanayei, Y., Ismail, N and Talebi, S. M (2009): Determination of Heavy Metals in Zayandeh Rood River, Isfahan-Iran. *World Applied Science Journal* 6(9) : 1209- 1214.
- Singh S, Mosley LM. Trace metals level in drinking water on Viti Levu, Fiji islands. *The south pacific journal of natural and Applied science.* 2003;21(1):31-34.
- Wakida, F.T., Lara-Ruiz, D., Temores-Pena, J., Rodriguez-Ventura, J. G., Diaz, C and Garcia-Flores, E (2008): Heavy metals in sediments of the Tecate River, Mexico. *Environmental Geology*, 54: 637-642.